

MoonBase VR: Learning to program in a virtual reality game

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ABSTRACT

The idea of computer programming is quite abstract and can be challenging for novices. Learning how to write code is like learning a foreign language, but without the ability to compare the new words with native ones. To overcome this obstacle to learning, current computer science teaching can employ many creative ways to teach coding. Visual aids can be used to transfer the basic concepts of programming across to new students; helping them visualize the functional elements of coding. Learning through gamification is a method also deployed by educators, and has been a proven technique to improve learning outcomes. In this study, our research aims were to investigate the gamification of computer programming using virtual reality. Immersive technology such as virtual reality provides a promising framework to deliver visualization and gamification to better convey foundational programming concepts. To test this theory, a virtual reality game was constructed which provided a self-directed learning path through a simple game narrative. Study participants (n=40) immersed within the virtual environment were provided with the opportunity to build a fundamental understanding of programming. The outcomes of the study showed that there is an interest to learn computer programming within a VR game such as this one.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Applied computing** → Education; Interactive learning environments; • **Hardware** → Emerging technologies; Emerging interfaces; • **Software and its engineering** → Software notations and tools; General programming languages; Language types; Object oriented languages; • **Human-centered computing** → Interaction design; Interaction design process and methods; Activity centered design.

KEYWORDS

Virtual Reality, Gamification, Programming, Education, Computing

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ICIEI 2023, April 13–15, 2023, Manchester, United Kingdom

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ACM ISBN 979-8-4007-0061-3/23/04.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3594441.3594454>

ACM Reference Format:

Raymond Holder, Mark Carey, Patrick Walder, and Paul Keir. 2023. Moon-Base VR: Learning to program in a virtual reality game. In *2023 The 8th International Conference on Information and Education Innovations (ICIEI 2023)*, April 13–15, 2023, Manchester, United Kingdom. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 7 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3594441.3594454>

1 INTRODUCTION

In an attempt to increase the interest in students undertaking computer science, much effort has gone into developing tools and activities for young people [12]. Visual programming, in various forms, is one of the tools that has been developed to tackle the barriers to entry into computer programming. The ‘writing’ of the computer code is implemented through a graphical user interface making it simpler for the user. With visual programming tools, a student can develop their knowledge of programming in a fun and non-threatening way. Gamification techniques can be added to the learning process and are usually implemented using established gaming elements such as object manipulation, points scoring, time limits and achievement rewards. These games can be deployed to encourage & engage students whereas in an educational setting it has been shown to hold considerable potential as a means to enhance students’ motivation and engagement in the learning task, as well as enjoyment [13]. Employing effective pedagogic approaches, like game-based learning, should be a priority in education to maintain high-quality teaching and promote lifelong learning [28]. Virtual Reality (VR) is gaining popularity and becoming more affordable, allowing the technology to enter into education as a tool. Therefore, the effectiveness of using VR learning environments should be further explored [27]. It will be necessary to measure the user’s performance when engaging in a new technology to ensure there is a benefit to the learning process. User responses, from studies like this one, can serve to iteratively enhance the VR system and the application design [4, 39].

Many have spoken about the need for innovative traditional teaching [1, 5, 32]; putting pressure on the educational sector to advance the delivery of learning outcomes using newer technologies and novel approaches. Studies have shown VR has successfully deployed learning experiences in education and that students have been more engaged and with a higher level of knowledge retention [8, 15, 23, 25]. With the ever-evolving innovation in technology and its use, further studies need to be undertaken to provide the groundwork for a pedagogical framework that explores the best practices of design & deployment [36]. Therefore, game developers

Figure 1: Moonbase VR game images showing (left to right) the moon base environment, the coding problem and code blocks, the hologram project of the level to solve and a player building the program.

and educators need to start to think about how to use VR in the classroom to provide an improved learning experience.

Research results showed that fully immersive 3D learning environments will promote a learner’s interest and motivation compared with learning in a 2D animated environment [20]. In addition, the novelty of VR technology as a multisensory user experience promotes a learner’s motivation through engaging media [16]. Elements of interaction, imagination, and immersion are the main characteristics to engage and motivate students to learn in a VR environment. Through interactive and potentially high repetition, VR can help to improve knowledge retention and student motivation [4].

This study builds on research that has already been performed on the flat-screen application Scratch [21]. Taking the concepts from Scratch, a virtual reality application has been developed for this study (Figure 1) that utilizes the block-based visual programming method. However, the study implements using an immersive 3D environment instead of a flat screen to teach the fundamentals of computer programming. A user of the application will be placed in a virtual environment (a virtual moon base) where they take control of a humanoid robot avatar using VR equipment. The player must complete several tasks to avoid a disaster on the moon base. These tasks are to build a computer program by interacting with some 3D logic blocks that represent certain actions and allow the user to build small logical commands. If completed correctly, instructions are sent to guide a maintenance robot around the moon base. In total there are 10 short levels for the players to complete, each increasing in difficulty, and building on the last, to increase the programming knowledge of the player. The study wants to research if using VR will increase the user’s engagement in the tasks and considers whether this has a beneficial effect on the knowledge, understanding and enjoyment of programming concepts and fundamentals.

1.1 Gamification

The rise of the digital game medium as an academic field of study is expanding year after year following the trend seen with the escalation of digital games’ influence in entertainment and popular culture. According to the Association for UK Interactive Entertainment (UKIE), the success of digital games in the commercial entertainment industry has spurred research into their effects and relevance in the digital age [35].

The gains made by the digital game medium have motivated its adoption for pursuits beyond entertainment. A developing approach in this area is gamification, which has been predominantly, though inconsistently, referred to as the selective inclusion of game-like

elements into an interactive game without building out a fully-fledged game [10, 11]. Generally, this phrase is used to describe the interactive features that aims to motivate and engage by using game elements and mechanics. Thus far, no standard definition has been agreed upon, similarly, there is little consistency regarding the conceptual framework of what gamification encompasses.

Response to the use of digital games in education has been polarized in academic research [3], with exploratory publications varying from complete rejection to curiosity [2, 9, 19]. The early development of the platform creates an opportunity for the study of gamification as an object of investigation, an alternative approach to curriculum design, and a computer-facilitated phenomenon [33].

Gamification in education refers to the inclusion of game features on top of existing learning activities. Adding gamification elements does not primarily alter the fundamental approach to the activity, it may make students more engaged in the learning outcomes [26], particularly through the introduction of competitive attributes. Gamification is particularly different from gaming, as here game values are engaged to a deeper level. Many of today’s gamified educational activities incorporate tasks with gamification features layered over the top; to fully-fledge games which have been remodeled for use in education. Both gamification and gaming may be associated with computer, mobile & web-based platforms [17]. Simple games may come in the form of drill-based or quiz-based educational apps, while more developed applications can come in the form of augmented and virtual reality games.

In the field of education, there is considerable interest in using games to motivate and engage student learning [22, 26]. This interest is fed by the idea of deploying gaming as a “fun” way to engross students in a topic. The hope is that the enjoyment of playing digital games gives the student proficiency in the curriculum subject matter in an effortless manner. Compared to players of popular casual games, players of educational simulation games perform complex procedural knowledge-related operations; thus, greater focus and involvement in the game and its learning content during the gaming process are required [6].

The utilization of gamification may not always be beneficial for an academic application, but it can be used as a mechanism to enhance motivation [37]. It must be carefully developed, with the user in mind, to achieve an increase in enthusiasm. This work addressed questions about teachers’ use of analogue or virtual games to analyze if gamification has a basis for interested people in the teaching community.

1.2 Visual Programming (Scratch)

Visual programming environments are widely used to introduce young people to computer science and programming; in particular, they encourage learning by exploration with several applications being used in educational institutions such as; Scratch, Kodable, Roblox Coding, Code.org & LightBot. Scratch is a visual programming platform that allows its primary users aged 8 to 16 to work on personal expressive projects such as animated stories and games while learning to code. Self-directed learning through playing and cooperation with others is a key design goal of Scratch. Each day, Scratchers (Scratch users) from around the world upload more than 1,500 new projects to the site, with source code freely available for sharing and remixing [31]. The site’s assortment of projects is widely varied, including video games, interactive newsletters, science simulations, virtual tours, birthday cards, and interactive tutorials, which all have been coded in Scratch. As Scratchers learn important mathematical and computational concepts, as they code, program and share projects they also learn soft skills such as; thinking creatively, systematically reasoning, and working collaboratively which are arguably all essential skills for the 21st century [7].

Many young people are very articulate at sending text messages, playing online games, and browsing the Web. It has become commonplace to refer to young people as “digital natives” [30] due to their apparent fluency with digital technologies, but does that make them fluent with new technologies? Though they interact with digital media frequently, few can create their own games, and animations. or simulations [18]. It is as if they can “read” but not “write.” The ability to program computers provides important benefits, for example, how you can express yourself and what you can create with the computer is greatly increased. It also broadens the gamut of what can be learnt. In particular, programming supports “computational thinking” helping to learn important problem-solving and design strategies (such as modularization and iterative design) that carry over to nonprogramming domains [38]. Visual programming can build the foundations of a path to becoming fluent in computer programming and many professional game engine applications such as Unity, Unreal Engine & Godot, include visual scripting systems for the developer to quickly create these applications and are being used to build interactive experiences, visualization for film & architecture, and game development.

2 THE GAME (MOON BASE VR)

In this section, we discuss the various stages of our educational game’s development, including pre-production, best practices and prototyping of a virtual reality game. The platform we focus on is the Oculus PC (now Meta) platform.

The virtual reality game development process is very similar to development on other platforms such as mobile, PC & console. However, developing for a virtual reality device can include some major differences such as designing for specific inputs, like the Touch motion controllers; ensuring your players are comfortable in the game, and finding out who the target audience is and what their interests are. What might be thrilling to play on a PC or console may not be as exhilarating in VR due to the nature of the platform.

VR gives players something special, something they can’t get with anything else, full immersion.

The very first stage of game development is pre-production. During the pre-production stage, we defined ideation and started planning out and designing the VR experience. All research on the resources we intended to use, the art and narrative references and the target audience was completed before building the game.

We considered how to find and develop our target audience. VR audiences are quite varied these days and different VR devices tend to pull different audiences. We are focused on PCVR that have motion-tracked controllers (Figure 2) instead of headset tracking only VR systems since these allow more interactivity we tried to make the most of the technology so players could use the controllers and interact with the virtual environment. Most importantly, we wanted to make sure the in-game interactions felt solid and fun. Exploring user profiles for the game is essentially finding the ideal player, the person who would be interested in and will get the most out of the game and we built it around that person. For this study, we targeted a personality type who is new to computer programming but likes to play games and has an interest in new technologies.

We asked the questions:

What will the player be doing in the game?

How will they do it?

We found ways to guide the user to points of interest through sound and visuals with text and voiceovers to deliver the narrative. We took extra care when including transitions and making sure to consider the user when designing them as these can be jarring in VR.

As VR becomes more widespread, developers explore the limits of the technology, and a list of ‘best practices are starting to come together. Here are just a couple of the prominent examples we found when developing the game. We made sure to display which buttons do what to show the player an in-game controller in the player’s field of view when opening the first level (Figure 2). Most players don’t know what a grip versus a trigger is; or where the A B X Y buttons are, so we gave an opening level where the player could explore freely while learning the controls & movement. Our game offered teleportation and ‘ghost’ walking options (Figure 2). Both options limit the possibility of a user feeling motion sickness, the ghost walking option showed the player’s avatar walking to a location while the player’s camera remained static until the user ended the movement and they would then teleport to the location. Implementing teleportation has some benefits and is typically comfortable for all players. Since teleportation can be less immersive in VR, many developers choose to have teleportation as a secondary form of locomotion. We prototyped basic mechanics like picking up objects, throwing objects, and putting objects together. Getting this out of the way grounded us and informed the rest of the game. Picking up an object was found to be a pain point with some users unfamiliar with VR and the controllers, we, therefore, applied the grip/drop function to the ‘grip’ button at the side of the controller and the trigger button placed at the front of the controller. The game has realistic physics collisions. While the player is gripping a code block, if thrown or dropped, the object will act under gravity; albeit the reduced gravity of the Moon. A highlight and snap function was implemented for any object (like the code blocks)

Figure 2: (left to right) menu UI, console with controllers functions, the player handling a code block, ghost walking movement.

that could be joined together (Figure 1). Once a player picks up an object, an invisible search function is implemented. If another object that can be joined together is found in the search range, then a translucent green ‘ghost’ image is shown to the player to indicate that the object can be connected; and where the placement would take place. Once the object is released, it will snap to the location. We also prototyped art, sound and user interfaces; and tested all these aspects in VR before confirming their inclusion and proceeded to create a vertical slice; a prototype version of the game that demonstrates how the full game should look and feel. A typical first vertical slice should be representative of character art, environmental art and game mechanic functionality. The first vertical slice needed to be ready for undertaking the study. After several interim builds, we had our first prototype.

3 THE STUDY

In this section, we outline how the study was carried out and how the data was collected. The first phase of the study gathered data on the general perceptions around the use of virtual reality and VR’s use within computer science education. The information gathered from a targeted questionnaire aimed at both experienced VR users and non-VR users detects the perceptions of VR for use in higher education. 40 participants were recruited to undertake the study, and a call for participants by email was sent out throughout our school within the university, with posters placed around the campus and word-of-mouth support.

During the first phase of the experiment, participants were placed in VR and played the game either for around 20 minutes; until they had completed the game; or until they felt like they wanted to stop. They explored all the features that the game provided until an unavoidable end to the game. Once the participant finished the game and removed the headset, they were asked to complete a post-experiment survey with questions about their experience presented on a standard assessment scale from 1 to 5 for each question (a Likert scale). The survey had questions related to gameplay; design of the game & environment; menu navigation; interface design; animation; and character movement; as well as a feedback section where the participant was allowed to write freely about their personal thoughts for future improvements.

A NASA-TLX [14] method form was used as a post-test to assess the mental workload that the participant was exposed to while performing the activity. The NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) is an assessment tool developed in the 1980s to assess the ‘workload’ of a user undertaking a task. The workload is measured by asking the participants to complete a questionnaire on how demanding a task was. This is divided into 6 categories: Mental Demand, Physical Demand, Temporal Demand, Performance, Effort & Frustration. It is a widely accepted form of assessing performance and implemented

here will allow for comparison between participants’ perceived workloads offering an insight into the effectiveness of the application of VR for learning computer code. This gave a good amount of data to build a basic understanding of the application allowing for further research in the future with larger groups. The experiment was conducted as a technical feasibility analysis rather than a human-centred approach. We gathered all data from the experiment and used a unique identifier key for the dataset.

The study gathered data from each participant to gain an understanding of the effectiveness of the learning application and to assess the technical feasibility of the VR application in computer science teaching, through repetition and reinforcement; in presenting and building the logic blocks, and finally, a verbal and written debrief was presented to the participant by the principal investigator immediately after the experiment.

4 FINDINGS

A total of 40 participants were selected to undertake the study. All of the participants were asked to complete a pre-experience questionnaire, and post-experience questionnaire; and to complete the NASA TXL survey to find the level of subjective workload.

4.1 Pre-experience questionnaire

The pre-experience survey questions have been used to understand general trends in the study group, and how much prior experience they have had with virtual reality, computer programming & educational games. 87.5% of the participants identified as male with the rest (12.5%) identifying as female. The largest age group represented in the study were 15 to 30-year-olds (62.5%), 30 to 45 was the second largest section (27.5%) with a small proportion (10%) in the over-45 age group. At 47.5%, nearly half of the participants have a bachelor’s degree as their highest level of education, with high school making up just under a third (30%), then a master’s degree at 15% & a Ph.D. at 7.5%.

From this survey, we found a good spread of level of VR experience among the participants, with just over a third having an intermediate level, followed by just under a third of beginners and another third is made up of experienced, expert and no experience at all. At 57.5% a slightly larger portion of participants had previous experience with using visual scripting systems. Object-orientated programming is one of the main methods widely used in computer game development (as well as other computing fields), and a larger portion (62.5%) of participants have experience in this form of programming.

All of the participants had used VR before this study but only a small portion (15%) of the participants had used VR in an educational setting. As shown in Figure 3, History & science are the

Figure 3: Q5.3. If you have tried VR for education, in what area(s)?

largest fields where people had experienced a VR learning experience. Arts, English & Mathematics do not have anyone experiencing these in a VR educational application.

4.2 Post-experience questionnaire

The post-experience survey finds how the participants feel about the virtual reality experience and were undertaken shortly after they had finished playing through the game. The participant was presented with a statement and asked to grade how they felt about the statement with levels of 1 to 5 to strongly agree (level 1) through to strongly disagree (level 5). The participant was also asked for further comment at the end of the survey, allowing them to give feedback or comment on any aspect of the experience that may not have been covered in the standard questions.

When asked whether the headset and controllers are comfortable a large majority of the participants were middle of the road, by neither strongly agreeing nor disagreeing with the statement “The headset and joysticks are comfortable to use” and most people liked the look of the game, with 100% scoring it level 3 and above but not many people felt discomfort while playing the game in VR, with 90% of participant saying they had little to no dizziness. With the movement options in the game, most participants found using the joystick movement fairly easy to use, with respondent grading at level 2 or 3 out of 5 making a combined 80% of the overall total. Nobody found it very difficult to use. 90% of participants used teleport movement to get around in the environment, with 60% using Ghost walking and 42.5% trying to navigate by walking in the real world. A large number of people used a combination of 2 or 3 movement methods with level 2 (quite useful) as the majority opinion for using the joystick to turn left or right as intuitive.

Looking at the appearance of the blocks and the ability to connect them we find a large number of participants found the placement highlighting feature useful, with a combined 67.5% of them scoring it as level 1 & 2 for usefulness. Most people (75%) found the initial position adequate for the experience, with only 10% of participants finding the placement could be improved. There was not much difference between levels 1, 2 & 3 in finding the way to blocks as intuitive with 27.5%, 30% & 25% respectively; so demonstrating that the method of snapping the blocks together worked well. When asked about the look of the different code blocks and how they represent the programming function we find levels 2 & 3 gain the highest marks here, with participants finding the appearance of the blocks correct. Similar results for the participants understanding of the use of the blocks were demonstrated in the survey results.

We also see 40% of the participants found that the difficulty of the game increases progressively with 100% giving a grade of 3 and

Figure 4: It did not take me long to understand what I have to do.

Figure 5: The difficulty of levels is reasonable.

Figure 6: Game Engagement

above in agreeing with the statement “The difficulty of the game increases progressively at each level”. Nearly half of the participants strongly agreed that the number of actions to solve a level is at the appropriate level. Most people found that the environment looked nice and that these environmental elements did not distract them from the tasks. Nobody disagreed with the statement that the transitions between the levels were smooth, with most people giving a level 1 or 2 here.

There is quite a spread of opinions when the participant was asked how long it took them to understand the game tasks, 65% graded levels 1 & 2 to agree it did not take too long and 35% selected levels 3, 4 & 5 to disagree (Figure 4). Most people found the difficulty of the level reasonable, and 77.5% agreed or strongly agreed with the statement (Figure 5). 75% of the participants agreed or strongly agreed that programming with this application can be fun, with the other 25% giving a level 3 and nobody disagreeing or strongly disagreeing and most people (95%) found the game engaging, the other 5% giving it a level 3 response (Figure 6).

When asked if visualising code using the code blocks in VR made it easier to understand programming the majority agreed

Q8. Does undertaking visual programming using VR reality gamification increase your interest to learn computer science?
40 responses

Figure 7: Q8. Does undertaking visual programming using VR gamification increase your interest to learn computer science?

somewhat and agreed with the statement (72.5%); 22.5% strongly agreed and the rest (5%) somewhat disagreed. Nobody strongly disagreed. The largest number of participants (37.5%) agreed that they were able to easily perform the tasks, and 1 person strongly disagreed with the statement “You were able to perform the task easily”. Finally, the participants were asked, “Does undertaking visual programming using VR reality gamification increase your interest to learn computer science?”.

Figure 7 shows a large portion of the participants (75%) found that undertaking visual programming using a VR game increased their interest to learn computer programming, with 2.5% saying it would not increase their interest and the rest (22.5%) saying it may increase their interest.

4.3 Feedback and comments

A few responses about the experience from the participants are listed below:

- “an interesting way to build code”
- “I think that the idea of visualizing code in this way is very intuitive and makes the whole process fun to carry out and fun to learn. . .I wanted the blocks to be a more complex arrangement where the nesting inside and outside of loops and conditional statement was more visually represented.”
- “it keeps you highly engaged with the task and makes the code easy to understand as you can see what it does.”
- “The environment looks great, and the overall experience is very engaging. . .I would have really enjoyed moving to a level where the code was not provided. . .something that would take more time would be more advanced (yet fundamental) concepts of computer programming such as function calls and recursion.”

4.4 NASA-TLX

To calculate a TLX score the average raw score is taken from the scale of each associated workload factor and is multiplied by the average and then divided by the combined weights. For this study, the data gathered from the participants were entered into an online TXL calculator to output the final average group score. As shown in Table 1, a high workload score is seen as a less acceptable level of workload; with a score greater than 70 deemed a demanding workload. Workload levels below 50 are considered acceptable [24], and participants in this study gained an overall NASA-TLX score of 39 with the breakdown of the results seen in Table 2.

Table 1: The mental workload scale [29]

Workload	Value
Low	0-9
Medium	10-29
Somewhat high	30-49
High	50-79
Very high	80-100

Table 2: Gathered results

Category	Average score	Weight
Mental Demand	40	5
Physical Demand	30	1
Temporal Demand	40	2
Performance	45	2
Effort	40	4
Frustration	25	1

5 CONCLUSION

In this article, we described Moonbase VR, a programming game in virtual reality. We created a VR programming language that is highly visual while being semantic. To evaluate Moonbase VR, we have performed a study with a total of 40 participants to examine: the usability of manipulating code blocks within a virtual reality game to build computer programs effectively, and the participants perception of using a VR game to learn programming. We found that a large majority of the participant felt that using a virtual reality game offered a fun and engaging way to learn to program and it would increase the interest in this part of computer science. Moonbase VR is inspired by the possibilities of programming in VR and further development of the platform could see a more complex implementation of the concepts demonstrated here. For instance, an educator could upload their learning outcomes via a text document, spreadsheet, or a graphical interface, allowing them to tailor the gameplay to meet the specific requirement of their students’ needs. Building further ‘puzzle’ mechanics that also utilize the code blocks to build a set of instructions to run a problem-solving problem; or implementing multi-user/player functionality so students can work together to build the code or allow the teacher to observe and guide a student undertaking the tasks.

Given the great potential for VR to enhance our learning outcomes [34] we have shown that utilizing a VR game like Moonbase VR can help teach programming concepts. Although further development of the application and assessment research should be conducted to confirm the expectations empirically. Our findings show that there is reason to be excited about what virtual reality will bring to computer science education.

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